

Manifesto Readability in India: Populist vs. Complex Approaches to Political Communication

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ABSTRACT: This study evaluates the readability of 2024 Lok Sabha election manifestos from India's three major political parties: Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), Indian National Congress (INC), and Communist Party of India (Marxist) CPI(M). Utilizing the Flesch Reading Ease and Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level formulas, the analysis assesses the accessibility of welfare, development and infrastructure, and national security sections within these manifestos. Findings reveal that all manifestos exhibit moderate to high complexity levels, potentially limiting comprehension among average voters. The BJP's manifesto is consistently the most complex across all sections, while the INC and CPI(M) present relatively more accessible texts subsequently making their approach less populist in their election manifesto documents. The study underscores the need for simplifying political communication to enhance democratic engagement.

KEY WORDS: Manifesto, Democracy, Readability, Lok Sabha Election, India.

INTRODUCTION:

Election manifestos have become an effective source of political communication in the offline and online campaigns to influence voting behaviour (Berger & Jager, 2024). Political communication in India in the recent time has changed drastically leaving the scope for understanding the role played by the election manifesto promises in influencing voting behaviour. Candidate, party, ideology, caste, religion coupled with media and newspaper-reading habits and systemic pressures, make political decision-making a complex and dynamic process in India (Banerjee & Chaudhuri, 2018). However, these studies done in the Indian context ignore one factor of political communication that can have major impact on voters' political decision making, that is the election manifesto promises. Election manifestos play a critical role in this context by influencing voter behaviour and shaping electoral outcomes. Research highlights their importance in presenting policy programs that resonate with voters, as observed in Ghana's Fourth Republic, where manifestos have shifted focus from ethno-social dynamics to policy content (Akeliwira & Mensah, 2022). Additionally, language complexity in manifestos significantly affects their readability and effectiveness. Studies have shown that populist parties tend to use simpler language, enhancing voter understanding, while others use complex language to articulate nuanced policy positions (Bischof & Senninger, 2018; Gyasi, 2023).

Despite extensive research on manifesto readability in global contexts, similar studies in India are scarce. This gap is critical in a democratic setup like India, where election manifestos serve as a tool for political communication. To address this, the present study focuses on the 2024 Lok Sabha election manifestos of three major political parties—Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), Indian National Congress (INC), and Communist Party of India (Marxist) (CPI(M)). These parties represent distinct ideological positions—right-wing (BJP), centre-left (INC), and left-wing (CPI(M))—making their manifestos an ideal subject for comparative textual analysis (Verma, 2022). The study will analyse manifestos written in English, a lingua franca in India, particularly among urban and educated populations. English-medium manifestos allow for broader accessibility and reflect strategic positioning on national and global issues. The growing prevalence of English as a medium of education further supports this choice; enrolment in English-medium schools has seen significant growth in recent years, highlighting its increasing relevance (Nagarajan, 2015). By conducting a readability analysis, this research aims to evaluate whether the language used in these manifestos is accessible or overly complex, thereby impacting voter engagement and the democratic process. This study seeks to fill the gap in the Indian context by providing insights into how political parties communicate their promises to the electorate through manifestos.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Electoral manifestos have long been regarded as instruments through which political parties communicate their priorities, policies, and vision to the electorate. Berger and Jager (2024) examine the influence of electoral manifestos on the online communication strategies of electoral candidates, concluding that manifestos significantly shape their messaging. While this research provides a rich context-specific analysis, its limited geographic focus raises questions about the generalizability of its findings to more diverse democratic systems, such as India's. Similarly, Banerjee and Chaudhuri (2018) explore the influence of voters' newspaper preferences and occupations on political party selection, finding that specific voter age categories also significantly impact decision-making. However, their reliance on print media influence leaves out potential factor like election manifesto promises. Rodrigues (2020) presents a framework for understanding the shift of political communication in India from traditional platforms to the social media platforms provides valuable insights on the political communication scenario in the recent times in India. However, the study fails to incorporate the nature of political communication presented through the promises made by the political parties in India. Varughese and Semetko (2022) in their research observes how massive rallies and misinformation on social media changed the political communication game in India but ignores the approach of the political parties in conveying their promises to the masses. From these researches cited above, we can observe that political communication, particularly through election manifestos, emerges as a pivotal yet underexplored factor in influencing voter behaviour in India. Bischof and Senninger (2018) highlight the impact of language simplicity in campaign materials on voter comprehension and perception. Their findings suggest that populist parties often use straightforward language to bridge the gap

between policy communication and voter understanding, positioning themselves effectively in the ideological space. This analysis, although insightful, primarily examines Western democracies, leaving questions about how language strategies in manifestos function in multicultural and multilingual contexts like India. Further supporting the significance of manifestos in political communication, Akeliwira and Mensah (2022) document a shift in Ghana's Fourth Republic from ethno-social dynamics to policy-driven narratives in manifestos. However, Gyasi (2023) points out a critical limitation in this domain: party manifestos in Ghana, regardless of their policy focus, were uniformly written at a complexity level beyond the average voter's comprehension. This raises broader questions about the accessibility of political documents in democratic processes, particularly in countries with high literacy diversity. Despite the robust scholarship on manifesto readability and its influence on voter behaviour in Western and African contexts, there is a glaring research gap in the Indian context. Existing studies on voting behaviour in India focus on socio-demographic factors, such as caste, religion, and ideology, without adequately addressing the role of manifestos as tools of political communication. While research outside India underscores the potential of manifestos to influence voter perceptions and decisions, there is limited understanding of how Indian political parties use manifestos to communicate their ideologies and promises, especially considering the linguistic diversity and literacy variations across the country.

This study seeks to address these gaps by analysing the 2024 Lok Sabha election manifestos of three ideologically distinct political parties—Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), Indian National Congress (INC), and Communist Party of India (Marxist) (CPI(M)). By focusing on the readability and accessibility of these English-language manifestos, the research will evaluate how effectively these documents communicate with an educated and urban electorate. This research helps assess whether manifestos align with the linguistic abilities of these emerging English-speaking voters or whether they remain overly complex and disconnected from their reading levels., offering a novel contribution to the literature on political communication in India.

METHODOLOGY:

This study aims to evaluate the complexity and accessibility of the language used in political manifestos, with the objective of determining whether the text is suitable for the average Indian voter. To achieve this, the study employed two widely recognized readability formulas: the Flesch Reading Ease Score and the Flesch Kincaid Grade Level Score (Solnyshkina et al., 2017). These formulas provide quantitative measures of the readability of each manifesto available in the English text, allowing for an assessment of how easily the general public can comprehend the promises and commitments outlined by the political parties. The Flesch Reading Ease Score is a metric used to evaluate how easy or difficult a text is to read, based on factors like sentence length and word complexity. The formula used is:

$$\text{Reading Ease Score} = 206.835 - (1.015 \times \text{ASL}) - (84.6 \times \text{ASW})$$

- **ASL** refers to the average sentence length, which is calculated by dividing the total word count by the number of sentences.
- **ASW** stands for the average syllables per word, determined by dividing the total syllable count by the total number of words.

The score ranges from 0 to 100, with higher scores signifying easier readability. The score can be interpreted as follows:

- **90-100:** Suitable for an average 11-year-old reader.
- **60-70:** Appropriate for readers aged 13-15.
- **0-30:** Best suited for university graduates.

A higher score means the text is easier to read and could be more accessible to a wider audience, particularly those with less formal education.

In addition, the Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level offers another way to assess readability, indicating the U.S. school grade level required to comprehend the text. The formula is:

$$\text{Grade Level} = (0.39 \times \text{ASL}) + (11.8 \times \text{ASW}) - 15.59$$

- **ASL** is the average sentence length (total words divided by total sentences).
- **ASW** is the average syllables per word (total syllables divided by total words).

This score translates into a corresponding grade level:

- A score of **8.0** indicates that the text is understandable by an 8th-grade student, around 13-14 years old.

RESULT:

The readability analysis of the welfare, development and infrastructure and national security sections of the manifestos (See Table 1, Table 2, Table 3) from India's three major political parties—BJP, INC, and CPI(M)—reveals significant differences in accessibility, particularly when considering the diverse literacy levels across the electorate. English is not the mother tongue of the majority of Indians; rather, it is a foreign language. The average fluency of English speakers in India is modest, according to proficiency data. India received an EPI (English Proficiency Index) score of about 500 points out of 800 in the 2023 edition, placing it at number 60 in the world (Polscaru, 2024).

Table 1- Readability Scores of the Welfarist Promises

Metric	BJP	INC	CPI(M)
Words	5,354	5,095	4,321
Characters	31,147	27,458	25,433
Paragraphs	575	701	643
Sentences	230	253	222
Sentences per Paragraph	1.5	1.3	1.0
Words per Sentence	8.3	4.8	4.6
Characters per Word	5.8	5.5	5.8
Flesch Reading Ease Score	30.9	39.1	35.6
Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level	11.0	8.9	9.4
Passive Sentences	1.7%	9.4%	2.2%

Source: Computed by author

Table 2- Readability Scores of the Development and Infrastructure Promises

Metric	BJP	INC	CPI(M)
Words	6,287	4,302	973
Characters	36,868	22,409	6,088
Paragraphs	711	431	115
Sentences	274	213	9
Sentences per Paragraph	1.4	1.7	1.1
Words per Sentence	7.6	9.4	7.6
Characters per Word	5.8	5.1	5.6
Flesch Reading Ease Score	32.2	45.2	40.8
Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level	10.6	9.2	9.4
Passive Sentences	1.8%	6.5%	0.0%

Source: Computed by author

Table 3- Readability Scores of the National Security Promises

Metric	BJP	Congress	CPI(M)
Word Count	1,125	3,774	843
Characters	6,653	20,375	4,892
Paragraphs	120	124	138
Sentences	46	183	62
Sentences per Paragraph	1.5	1.9	1.1
Words per Sentence	7.3	19.6	4.3
Characters per Word	5.9	5.2	6.0
Flesch Reading Ease	26.1	34.8	29.7
Flesch-Kincaid Grade Level	11.4	13.2	10.1
Passive Sentences (%)	4.3%	31.6%	3.2%

Source- Computed by author

DISCUSSION:

Under the welfare section for the BJP's manifesto, the Reading Ease score ranges from 0 to 100, with a score of 30.9 indicating that the text is fairly difficult to read. This suggests that the content is likely suited for readers with at least a college-level education, potentially making it challenging for the general population, especially those with lower literacy levels. The Grade Level of 11.0 supports this, indicating that the text is written at an 11th-grade reading level, which aligns with the reading ease score, reinforcing that the manifesto may be more accessible to individuals with a higher educational background. The analysis also highlights that the average sentence length is 8.3 words, suggesting relatively concise sentences, which generally aids in comprehension. However, the brevity might reduce the depth of explanation, making complex ideas appear simpler than they are. Additionally, the analysis shows that the manifesto uses relatively long words, which often correlate with more complex ideas, contributing to the higher reading difficulty. A low percentage of passive sentences (1.7%) indicates that the manifesto predominantly uses an active voice, which is generally clearer and more direct, potentially making the arguments and promises more compelling and easier to follow. Overall, the readability statistics suggest that while the BJP's manifesto may be well-suited to educated voters, it could be challenging for a broader audience. Simplifying the language could enhance its accessibility and engagement with voters, particularly those with lower literacy levels.

In contrast, the INC's manifesto presents a slightly more accessible text. The Reading Ease score of 39.1, though still indicating difficulty, suggests it is somewhat easier to read than the BJP's. This score implies that the content is suitable for readers with at least a high school

education, but still might be challenging for those with lower literacy levels. The Grade Level of 8.9 suggests that the text is written at a 9th-grade reading level, making it more accessible than the BJP's manifesto. The average sentence length in the Congress manifesto is 4.8 words, indicating very concise sentences that improve readability by making the content easier to digest and understand. The average word length is 5.5 characters, slightly shorter than in the BJP's manifesto, which also contributes to the lower reading difficulty. However, the manifesto has a higher percentage of passive sentences (9.4%), which can make the text less direct and harder to follow, potentially weakening the clarity and persuasiveness of its arguments. Despite these challenges, the readability analysis suggests that the Congress manifesto is more accessible to a wider audience, particularly those with lower literacy levels, compared to the BJP's manifesto.

The CPI(M)'s manifesto falls between the BJP and INC in terms of readability. A Reading Ease score of 35.6 indicates that the text is difficult to read, though slightly easier than the BJP's and somewhat harder than the Congress's. This score suggests that the manifesto is aimed at an audience with at least a high school education but could be challenging for those with lower literacy levels. The Grade Level of 9.4 aligns closely with the Congress manifesto, indicating that the text is written at approximately a 9th-grade reading level. The average sentence length is 4.6 words, the shortest among the three, which generally enhances readability by making the material easier to follow. However, an average of 5.8 characters per word, similar to the BJP's, indicates the use of relatively long words, which may contribute to the higher reading difficulty. The manifesto also has a low percentage of passive sentences (2.2%), suggesting a preference for active voice, which improves clarity and directness. These readability statistics indicate that while the CPI(M)'s manifesto is challenging, it is designed to be accessible to a moderately educated audience, balancing clarity with some level of complexity.

Under the development and infrastructure segment (See Table 2), the Reading Ease scores reveal that the BJP manifesto scores the lowest (32.2), indicating that it is the most challenging to read among the three. This score suggests the text may be more suitable for an audience with higher literacy levels or more familiarity with technical or policy language. In contrast, Congress's manifesto, with a score of 45.2, is easier to read, while CPI(M)'s manifesto occupies an intermediate position with a score of 40.8. The Grade Level further supports this analysis, as the BJP's text requires a reading ability at approximately the 11th-grade level, compared to the Congress and CPI(M) manifestos, which are slightly less demanding, requiring around a 9th to 10th-grade reading level. This higher complexity in the BJP manifesto may reflect the party's intention to present detailed and nuanced policy positions, potentially at the expense of broader accessibility. The use of passive voice in a text can impact clarity and directness. CPI(M)'s manifesto uses no passive voice, indicating a clear and straightforward communication style, which could be perceived as more assertive and action-oriented. In contrast, Congress's manifesto employs passive voice in 6.5% of sentences, which might introduce a level of detachment or formality that can obscure the actor in policy statements, potentially making the text less engaging. The BJP's moderate use of passive voice (1.8%) suggests an attempt to balance clarity with the formal tone typical of policy documents.

The readability of the national security promises (See Table 3) varies significantly among the three political parties. The Reading Ease score indicates that all three manifestos are challenging to read, with scores below 50, which typically suggests the text is best understood by college graduates. The BJP's national security section has the lowest Reading Ease score (26.1), indicating it is the most complex and potentially difficult to understand, likely due to dense language or technical terminology. Congress's score of 34.8 is somewhat more accessible, but still complex, aligning with its longer sentence structure. CPI(M) falls in between with a score of 29.7, suggesting that while its text is concise, it still presents a certain level of complexity. The Grade Level scores further reinforce this, with Congress requiring the highest educational level (13.2), followed by BJP (11.4), and CPI(M) (10.1). The use of passive voice is minimal in both the BJP (4.3%) and CPI(M) (3.2%) manifestos, which suggests a more direct and active writing style. Active voice is typically easier for readers to follow and can make the text feel more engaging and dynamic. In contrast, Congress employs a significant amount of passive voice (31.6%), which can make the text feel more formal or detached, potentially increasing the complexity and reducing the immediacy of the communication.

CONCLUSION:

As previous studies have shown that populist parties tend to use simpler language, enhancing voter understanding, while others use complex language to articulate nuanced policy positions (Bischof & Senninger, 2018; Gyasi, 2023), in conclusion, we can observe that from the overall readability analysis, the manifesto promises of the three major political parties fall under the moderate to difficult readability score for an average Indian voter. The three major political parties in India are less populist in the approach of conveying the promises to the average Indian voter and more complex in articulating nuanced policy positions. Each party's approach to presenting their welfarist, development and infrastructure, national security based promises reflects their likely target audience. Congress appears to prioritize broader accessibility, CPIM balances clarity with complexity, and the BJP seems to focus on a more educated readership. due to dense language. Congress's promises are the most detailed and complex, with longer sentences and a high level of passive voice, making it more challenging for readers. CPI(M) offers the most concise and straightforward content, with short sentences and minimal use of passive voice, making it relatively easier to read, despite a moderate complexity level. This analysis suggests that while BJP and CPI(M) prioritize clarity and directness, Congress focuses on providing a more comprehensive and detailed discussion, though at the expense of readability. The insights derived from the analysis suggest that political parties in India should introduce guidelines or standards for manifesto readability to ensure that political communication is accessible to all voters, irrespective of their education or linguistic background.

Acknowledgement: The first author gratefully acknowledges the financial support under the UGC-NET Junior Research Fellowship (NTA Ref. No.: 210510063608) dated 19/02/2022 of the Ministry of Education, Govt. of India for Research in Social Sciences.

REFERENCES:

1. Akeliwira, G. A., & Owusu-Mensah, I. (2022). Manifestos and Voting Behavior in Third-Wave Democracies: Evidence from Ghana. *PanAfrican Journal of Governance and Development (PJGD)*, 3(2), 3-32.
2. Banerjee, S., & Ray Chaudhuri, B. (2018). Influence of voter demographics and newspaper in shaping political party choice in India: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Political Marketing*, 17(1), 90-117. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15377857.2016.1147513>
3. Berger, V. T., & Jäger, F. (2024). Do electoral candidates reflect or select campaign issues? The influence of electoral manifestos on online communication. *Party Politics*, 30(6), 1088-1099. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13540688231194704>
4. Bharatiya Janata Party. "2024 BJP Manifesto." Accessed June 23, 2024. <https://www.bjp.org/bjp-manifesto-2024>
5. Bischof, Daniel, and Roman Senninger. "Simple politics for the people? Complexity in campaign messages and political knowledge." *European Journal of Political Research* 57, no. 2 (2018): 473-495. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12235>
6. Communist Party of India (Marxist). "2019 CPI(M) Manifesto." Accessed June 23, 2024. <https://cpim.org/pressbriefs-cpim-election-manifesto/>
7. Gyasi, W. K. (2023). The readability of political party manifestos of the 2016 general elections in Ghana. *Athens Journal of Mass Media and Communications*, 9(1), 57-70. <https://doi.org/10.30958/ajmmc.X-Y-Z>
8. Indian National Congress. "2024 INC Manifesto." Accessed June 23, 2024. <https://manifesto.inc.in/>
9. Mukherjee, J., & Bernaisch, T. (2020). The development of the English language in India. In *The Routledge handbook of world Englishes* (pp. 165-177). Routledge.
10. Nagarajan, Rema (2015). "Number of Children Studying in English Doubles in 5 Years." *Times of India*. Accessed on 12 July, 2024, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/Number-of-children-studying-in-English-doubles-in-5-years/articleshow/49131447.cms>
11. Polscaru, Diana (2024). "How Many People in India Speak English." *The History of English*. Accessed on 12 July, 2024, <https://www.thehistoryofenglish.com/how-many-people-in-india-speak-english>
12. Rodrigues, U. (2020). Political communication on social media platforms. Platform capitalism in India, 221-238. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-44563-8_11
13. Solnyshkina, M., Zamaletdinov, R., Gorodetskaya, L., & Gabitov, A. (2017). Evaluating text complexity and Flesch-Kincaid grade level. *Journal of social studies education research*, 8(3), 238-248.
14. Verma, R. (2022). Promises that matter to Indian democracy: A study of election manifestos since 1952. *Centre for Policy Research*. cprindia.org/briefsreports/promises-that-matter-toindian-democracy-a-study-of-election-manifestos-since-1952, 05.
15. Varughese, A. M., & Semetko, H. A. (2022). Political campaigning in India: changing contexts of political communication. *South Asian History and Culture*, 13(3), 267-284. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19472498.2022.2093468>